

DRAPING TOOL GENERATION FOR IMAGE-BASED SURROGATE DRAPING MODELS USING FREE FORM DEFORMATION AND TOPOGRAPHY MODIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

In the context of composite manufacturing process development, digital twins are often used to conduct parametric studies in order to determine the optimum process parameters without the need of extensive trial-and-error experiments. Process simulation using finite element (FE) method has become a well-established tool for performing such tasks. However, the major drawback of this method is the high computational cost (especially in the context of preforming when draping dry materials), which restricts calculations to a limited set of configurations that must be carefully selected by experts. Therefore, modern approaches increasingly focus on surrogate modeling using artificial intelligence. One possible surrogate model architecture is the image-based U-Net model that maps input images to resulting output images. When trained with sufficient data, this kind of model is able to predict results for different draping parameters quite accurately for draping tool geometries included in the training data (see [1]). When it comes to unknown tool geometries (that were not within the training data), however, predictions become unreliable. This paper describes the generation of a parametric tool that covers a range of different tool geometries in order to expand the prediction accuracy for unseen geometries. By training the surrogate model on draping tools with different similarities to a reference, it can interpolate within this similarity range, enabling accurate predictions for unknown draping tools that lie between known configurations. The parametric tooling uses a similarity measure to evaluate the degree of similarity between two tools of different similarities to a certain reference tool. The goal is to use these generated tools within a routine to automatically create training data and then train the surrogate using the simulation results for the varying tools. The developed parametric draping tool uses Free Form Deformation and the *Downhill Simplex method* to achieve shapes of different similarities.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the last decades, artificial intelligence (AI)-based surrogate modeling became an increasingly popular strategy for approximating the complex behavior of various processes with faster yet still reliable alternatives. It is already applied across different disciplines such as biomedical applications [2], environmental science [3] or material science [4]. In the field of material forming and process simulation, there are also multiple applications in standard manufacturing such as metal forming [5, 6]. Most recent advances also show the use of surrogate models within the field of textile draping and composite manufacturing [7, 8]. Reported approaches range from rather low complexity (e.g., using linear regression models), to metamodeling [9] and neural networks of different complexities [10] up to highly complex full simulation models (e.g., using Position-Based Dynamics approaches) [8].

A quite common approach for the approximation of process parameters is the use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) – especially in form of a U-Net architecture. U-Nets, originating from the field of biomedical image segmentation [2], are supervised learning models, usually trained on labeled images, where each data entry contains an input with an associated output image. A properly trained model allows for a readily available prediction, with only moderately complex architecture.

In a preliminary study, we established the applicability of a U-Net surrogate model to predict the draping behavior of a fabric onto a rib tool [1]. Findings confirmed the ideal suitability of the image-based surrogate to approximate the draping behavior and provide accurate predictions for the rib tool geometry it was trained on. However, the main disadvantage of those kind of models is their poor extrapolation capabilities, meaning that the model cannot provide accurate predictions for draping tools that were not included in the training data. This means, if we want to use the surrogate model for a new draping tool geometry, a whole new training data, including the new tool geometry, must be generated annihilating the time-savings by this approach. The objective of this study is therefore to create a parametric tool that enables the generalization of the U-Net surrogate model in order to enhance the prediction quality of unseen geometries.

2 METHODS

The idea of creating a parametric draping tool is based on the assumption that U-Net surrogate models are capable of interpolating between similar solutions (i.e., data augmentation, see [2]). The surrogate model used in [1] should therefore be expanded by training with tools of different similarities, enhancing generalizability and thus, the overall applicability of image-based surrogate models. To implement this approach, we developed a python script that is able to targetedly modify surfaces based on a reference surface in order to achieve tools with different degrees of similarity to the reference. The following subsections show a detailed description of the generalization concept, script architecture, working principle and algorithm specifics.

2.1 Overall Objective and Generalization Concept

In the aircraft industry, component and draping tool design play a crucial role in ensuring the component’s structural integrity within the whole assembly. Oftentimes, tool geometries need to be slightly adapted in order to suit the varying application requirements. This results in various draping tools that differ in shape while still maintaining a certain degree of similarity. To ensure that the image-based surrogate model manages to deal with those kind of variations, they need to be reflected within the training data. In order to achieve that, we developed the following concept for the parametric tool creation:

First, a set of representative tool geometries (derived from real-world application components) must be defined. These serve as reference tools for creating variations with different degrees of similarity. The user provides their surface topology as *.stl* meshes. Examples of such geometries (e.g., based on typical aircraft components) are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Examples of representative reference tools for aircraft components: (a) spheric calotte, (b) saddle-shaped, (c) double sine and (d) curved hat profile

Modifications of such tools are always limited to manufacturing constraints, such as maximum z-displacements. Therefore, additionally to the reference tools, the user needs to define the manufacturing constraints that limit maximum displacements and thus the distortion of the whole profile. These displacement constraints are based on user expertise, resulting in a maximum possible “dissimilarity” for the tool variations of a respective reference.

For proof of concept, we used a double sine (i.e., *Usecase 1*) and a parabolic geometry (i.e., *Usecase 2*) as tool references:

Figure 2: Reference meshes for (a) *Usecase 1* and (b) *Usecase 2*.

The developed routine should systematically generate variations with different similarities to those two geometries, while satisfying the predefined manufacturing constraints (which define the maximum dissimilarity for each shape). In a subsequent step the variations can be used for training the surrogate model, enabling a generalization of the model.

2.2 Script architecture

The developed python script includes the targeted surface modification, similarity assessment and export of created tools as *.stl* files. It can be divided into three main building blocks composing the algorithm:

- a) Tool Deformation using Free Form Deformation (FFD)
- b) Similarity Measure
- c) Solver

Tool Deformation. The deformation of the tool is done via Free Form Deformation (FFD) using the python modules *splinepy* and *gustaf* [11]. This specific technique is used to deform geometrical objects by enclosing them with a hull based on 3D curves (e.g., B-splines or NURBS). By transforming the spline control points of the hull, the contained geometry can then be deformed [12] (see Figure 3). When selecting a reference tool (in our case an FE mesh, e.g., a double sine geometry), the number of spline points in each direction of a cartesian coordinate system can be specified. Distinct control points can then be selected to deform the tool.

Figure 3: Schematic sketch of the working principle of FFD for a (a) double sine geometry as initial configuration, (b) enclosed in a spline hull and an exemplary deformed configuration (c) with and (d) without spline hull.

Similarity Measure. The similarity measure used to assess the degree of similarity between a reference mesh and the deformed mesh is the root mean square value (*RMS*) of the nodal distances d_i between the reference mesh and the deformed mesh (see equation (1)).

$$RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_i d_i^2} \quad (1)$$

Different strategies for the similarity measure (such as the structural similarity index (SSIM) [13] or the comparison of histograms) were analyzed, however, the RMS measure provided the most suitable solution since the other approaches implied a loss of spatial correspondence (due to data summarization for histograms 2D conversion for SSIM).

Due to the manufacturing constraints explained above, the magnitude of the RMS value is limited to certain bounds. This constraint is implemented by calculating a maximum RMS value within predefined displacement bounds and normalizing the RMS value as shown in equation (2):

$$RMS_{norm} = \frac{RMS}{RMS_{max}} \quad (2)$$

This simultaneously ensures comparability between the RMS values of different configurations of the deformed mesh by normalizing the RMS value to a range of $[0,1]$. Spline control points can be displaced to achieve a certain similarity to the reference while considering the manufacturing constraints. The maximum possible RMS value is specific to the reference geometry as well as depending on the displacement bounds in z-direction. The RMS_{max} value is therefore determined in the following manner:

- (1) *Calculate Candidate z-values*. For each node in the reference mesh, the z-coordinate that lies furthest away from the point (within predefined bounds, either in positive or negative z-direction) is calculated.
- (2) *Enforce Neighbor Constraint*. The extreme values for the z-coordinates are adjusted so that a point does not exceed a fixed distance threshold to its neighbors. This is done iteratively until convergence.
- (3) *Local Refinement*. The z-values with respected neighbor constraints are then again optimized to maximize the deviation (i.e., the RMS value).

Figure 4 shows a schematic visualization of the working principle in a 2D case:

Figure 4: Schematic visualization of the working principle of the algorithm to determine RMS_{max} shown by the example of a 2D reference point cloud and the calculated (1) candidate values, (2) modified values based on the neighbor constraint and (3) refined values to maximize the RMS value.

Using this metric, different similarities to the reference within the design space can be determined by displacing the spline control points along the z-axis. Thereby, we can obtain shapes with different similarity to a reference, as demonstrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Possible solutions for (a) total dissimilarity (i.e., $RMS_{norm} = 0$), (b) medium similarity (i.e., $RMS_{norm} = 0.5$) and (c) total similarity ($RMS_{norm} = 1$) to the reference.

To automatically determine the spline displacement values necessary to achieve a possible configuration with target *RMS* value, we used the solver described in the following paragraph.

Solver. In order to determine a certain transformation array (i.e., array of z-displacements) for the spline control points to achieve a target similarity of the current deformed mesh to the reference mesh, an optimization algorithm was used. This algorithm enables a targeted topography modification to achieve a certain target value (T_v) for the similarity. Different optimization algorithms were analyzed on their suitability for the topography modification. For our purpose of optimizing the *RMS* value, we needed a derivative-free optimization algorithm, whereby the *Downhill Simplex Method* (also known as *Nelder-Mead method*) suited our application best since it allows for the optimization of non-linear functions with multiple parameters. In our case, the parameters to be optimized are the z-displacements of the spline control points and the objective function $f(\mathbf{x})$ to be minimized is the difference between the target value T_v and the normalized *RMS* value of the nodal distances $\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{x})$ between reference and deformed mesh (depending on the current z-displacement array \mathbf{x} of the spline points):

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = T_v - RMS_{norm}(\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{x})), \quad (3)$$

The found geometry for a specific T_v is thereby one candidate solution that depends on the chosen starting point \mathbf{x}_0 . Different starting points lead to different solutions which would all qualify for expanding the interpolation space of the surrogate model.

2.3 Topography Modification Procedure

Based on the three building blocks in section 2.1, the topography modification procedure is done using the *Downhill Simplex* algorithm combined with the FFD for the tool deformation and the similarity measure. Before delving into the working principle of the algorithm, we want to clarify the *terminology* to enhance understanding:

- A **vertex** (n -dimensional) in the context of the *Downhill Simplex Method* is one full candidate solution. It contains n entries which, in our case, reflects the number spline control points for which the z-displacement can be modified (e.g., $n = 16$).
- A **simplex** is a collection of $n + 1$ vertices (i.e., in our case, 17 arrays with dimension $n + 1$ each).
- The goal is to minimize the value of the **objective function** $f(\mathbf{x})$ where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ (in our case $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{16}$). We want to reach a certain degree of similarity based on the similarity measure RMS_{norm} . Therefore, our objective is to reach a target value T_v by:

$$\min|f(\mathbf{x})| = \min|T_v - RMS_{norm}(\mathbf{x})| \quad (4)$$

To get a clear understanding of the topography modification via *Downhill Simplex Method*, the 6 individual steps (performed within a loop) are as follows [14]:

0) Initialization of Simplex Δ

The procedure starts by defining a **starting point** \mathbf{x}_0 and a **step size** s . The starting point \mathbf{x}_0 is defined by our initial z-displacement of the spline points, which is an array of size n (i.e., number of modifiable spline points):

$$\mathbf{x}_0 = [x_{01}, x_{02}, \dots, x_{0n}] \quad (5)$$

The initial simplex Δ then consists of $n + 1$ entries, whereby \mathbf{x}_0 initially serves as our first vertex within the simplex:

$$\Delta = \{\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n\} \quad (6)$$

The residual 16 arrays are created by iteratively creating modified copies of \mathbf{x}_0 in the following manner:

$$\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{x}_0 + s \cdot \mathbf{e}_i, \quad (7)$$

where s is the defined step size and $\mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the standard basis vector with 1 in the i -th position and 0 elsewhere.

The objective function f is then evaluated at each entry of the simplex Δ , to get a score for each vertex:

$$f_i = f(\mathbf{x}_i) \quad \text{for } i \in [0, n], \quad (8)$$

resulting in a set of pairs:

$$\{(\mathbf{x}_i, f(\mathbf{x}_i))\}_{i=0}^n \quad (9)$$

1) Order Vertices

In a second step, the set of pairs is sorted by score, from best to worst: $f(\mathbf{x}_1) \leq f(\mathbf{x}_2) \leq \dots \leq f(\mathbf{x}_{n+1})$, with \mathbf{x}_1 being the vertex with the best score and \mathbf{x}_{n+1} being the vertex with the worst score.

2) Compute Centroid of Simplex

The centroid \mathbf{x}_c of the simplex is calculated without considering \mathbf{x}_{n+1} (i.e., without the array with the worst score):

$$\mathbf{x}_c = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{x}_i \quad (10)$$

3) Reflection

The worst vertex \mathbf{x}_{n+1} is then reflected using the centroid \mathbf{x}_c by:

$$\mathbf{x}_r = \mathbf{x}_c + \alpha(\mathbf{x}_c - \mathbf{x}_{n+1}), \quad (11)$$

with α being the reflection coefficient. The reflected vertex \mathbf{x}_r is then again evaluated using the objective function $f(\mathbf{x}_r)$. If \mathbf{x}_r achieves a better score than the second worst result \mathbf{x}_n , but not better than the best result \mathbf{x}_1 , the worst result \mathbf{x}_{n+1} is replaced by \mathbf{x}_r and the iteration is terminated:

$$\mathbf{x}_{n+1} \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_r \quad \text{if } f(\mathbf{x}_1) \leq f(\mathbf{x}_r) < f(\mathbf{x}_{n+1}) \quad (12)$$

Else the iterations move on to step 4a) or 4b), based on the score of the reflected vertex \mathbf{x}_r .

4a) If $f(\mathbf{x}_r) < f(\mathbf{x}_1)$: Expansion

If the reflected array \mathbf{x}_r achieves a better score than the best array \mathbf{x}_1 , the expansion step is performed as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}_e = \mathbf{x}_c + \gamma(\mathbf{x}_r - \mathbf{x}_c), \quad (13)$$

with γ being the expansion coefficient. If the evaluation of $f(\mathbf{x}_e)$ achieves a better score than $f(\mathbf{x}_r)$, the expanded array \mathbf{x}_e replaces the worst array \mathbf{x}_{n+1} :

$$\mathbf{x}_{new} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{x}_e & \text{if } f(\mathbf{x}_e) < f(\mathbf{x}_r) \\ \mathbf{x}_r & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_n \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_{new} \quad (15)$$

In either case, the current iteration is terminated, and the next iteration is started at step 1).

4b) If $f(\mathbf{x}_r) \geq f(\mathbf{x}_n)$: Contraction

In case that the reflected array \mathbf{x}_r performs worse than the second worst result \mathbf{x}_n , the contraction step is performed as follows:

- If $f(\mathbf{x}_r) < f(\mathbf{x}_{n+1})$: **Outside Contraction**

$$\mathbf{x}_{co} = \mathbf{x}_c + \gamma(\mathbf{x}_r - \mathbf{x}_c), \quad (16)$$

with γ being the contraction coefficient. If the contracted vertex \mathbf{x}_{co} performs better than the reflected vertex \mathbf{x}_r , the worst vertex \mathbf{x}_{n+1} is replaced by the contracted point \mathbf{x}_{co} (i.e., $\mathbf{x}_{n+1} \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_{co}$), the iteration is terminated and the next iteration is started at step 1). Else, the iteration continues with step 5).

- If $f(\mathbf{x}_r) \geq f(\mathbf{x}_{n+1})$: **Inside Contraction**

$$\mathbf{x}_{ci} = \mathbf{x}_c - \gamma(\mathbf{x}_{n+1} - \mathbf{x}_c), \quad (17)$$

with γ being the contraction coefficient. If the contracted vertex \mathbf{x}_{ci} performs better than the worst vertex \mathbf{x}_{n+1} , the worst vertex \mathbf{x}_{n+1} is replaced by the contracted point \mathbf{x}_{ci} (i.e., $\mathbf{x}_{n+1} \leftarrow \mathbf{x}_{ci}$) and the iteration is terminated (next iteration from step 1) on). Else, the iteration continues with step 5).

5) Reduction / Shrink (if expansion and contraction fail)

This step shrinks the simplex to narrow down to a local optimum, in case steps 3) and 4) fail. Thereby, all vertices of the simplex (except the best vertex \mathbf{x}_1) are replaced using:

$$\mathbf{x}_{red} = \mathbf{x}_1 + \sigma(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_1), \quad (18)$$

with σ being the shrink coefficient. That way, all vertices are moved towards the best vertex and the next iteration starts at step 1).

In our case, for each step from 3) to 5), the current mesh is modified (using the current parameter set of the simplex), the nodal distances to the reference mesh, the corresponding RMS value is calculated, and the objective function is evaluated. Based on the respective score of the objective function, a decision is made to terminate the iteration or to continue with a subsequent step. This process is repeated until a certain termination criterion (also checked within each evaluation step) is reached.

2.2.1 Dynamic penalty

The z-displacement constraints are implicitly contained in the target value through RMS_{max} . However, this constraint also needs to be forwarded to the solver in order to ensure parameter exploration within the constraints. Therefore, we adapted the *Downhill Simplex* algorithm by including a dynamic penalization approach. This penalty is designed to constrain the z-displacements in compliance with manufacturing constraints and thereby prevent excessive deformations. The idea behind the dynamic penalty is to discourage displacements that deviate significantly from the residual displacements:

First, the bounds for the tolerable distance range are calculated using the interquartile range (IQR) and the lower (b_l) and upper (b_u) bound are defined as:

$$b_l = Q1 - i * IQR, b_u = Q3 + i * IQR, \quad (19)$$

with $Q1$ and $Q3$ being the lower and upper quartile and i being a multiplier that can be adapted according to the desired sensitivity to outliers. The entries of the spline point displacement array \mathbf{x} are then filtered as 'below', 'above' or 'within' the bounds. For outliers below the lower bound, the individual penalty magnitude p_i is then calculated by:

$$p_i = (b_u - x_i)^2 \quad (20)$$

Similarly, the penalty for outliers above the upper bound is calculated as:

$$p_i = (x_i - b_l)^2 \quad (21)$$

We decided on a quadratic penalty function so that the solution performs exponentially worse with each point lying outside the IQR and with increasing distance. Before evaluating the individual score $f(\mathbf{x})$ of each step, the sum of all penalties $\sum p_i$ is added. This way, excessive distortions are considered rather unsuitable and the algorithm searches for alternative solutions.

2.3 Usecases for the Proof of Concept

For the proof of concept, we used the double sine and the parabolic geometry shown in Figure 2 as reference mesh and a plate geometry as initial mesh for the deformation. We conducted a parametric study with target values reaching from 0 (i.e., total dissimilarity) to 1 (i.e., identical meshes) in steps of 0.1 to evaluate the functionality of the developed routine. The hull for the FFD of our component consists of $4 \times 4 \times 2$ spline control points, whereas only the top control points ($n = 16$) were enabled for the z -displacement (i.e., displacement in height direction).

Figure 6: Spline hull for the deformation of the initial mesh for the usecases, with the modifiable control points marked in white.

This constraint was imposed to keep the calculation effort within a reasonable time. The parameters for the topography modification were chosen as follows:

- starting point $\mathbf{x}_0 = [0, 0, \dots, 0] \in \mathbb{R}^{16}$
- step size $s = 0.1$
- the reflection, expansion, contraction and shrink coefficients were set to standard values [14]:
 $\alpha = 1, \gamma = 2, \rho = 0.5, \sigma = 0.5$

The convergence criterion is based on the number of consecutive iterations with improvements below $10e^{-6}$. The procedure is terminated as soon as 100 consecutive improvements below that threshold are reached.

3 RESULTS

The parametric studies were conducted on the two generic geometries: the double sine and the parabolic geometry. The following sections contain the results of the RMS_{max} determination as well as the parametric study.

3.1 RMS_{max} for the Usecases

Usecase 1. The automatically determined value for RMS_{max} resulted in 0.3. This value is reached when the points of the deformed mesh are furthest away from the reference, without leaving the space bounds and without violating the constraint for excessive distortion. A surface with those extreme values is shown in Figure 7:

Figure 7: Configuration within the space bounds that leads to the highest RMS_{max} value for *Usecase 1* with reference mesh (blue) and modified mesh (red).

Usecase 2. As for *Usecase 1*, the maximum RMS value was automatically determined by calculating the deformed configuration which would lead to the largest distances between reference and deformed mesh. The RMS_{max} resulted in 0.3 (also similar to *Usecase 1*). The following figure shows the theoretical configuration that achieves the highest RMS value:

Figure 8: Configuration within the space bounds that leads to the highest RMS_{max} value for *Usecase 2* with reference mesh (blue) and modified mesh (red).

Even though these configurations are not possible to be reached using FFD (since the spline points always ensure a smooth surface without rough edges), they give an indication for the maximum possible RMS value that cannot be exceeded by any of the tool modifications using FFD – thus it is suitable for normalization.

3.2 Results Parametric Study for the Usecases

Usecase 1. The surface modification was performed using a double sine geometry as a reference mesh and a planar geometry as deformable mesh. An exemplary mesh modification result for $T_v = 1$, including the hull and the modified spline points, is shown in Figure 9. The initial mesh (Figure 9a) is deformed by modifying the top row of spline control points in order to achieve a configuration similar to the reference mesh (Figure 9b).

Figure 9: (a) Initial mesh and (b) deformed configuration for $T_v = 1$ with an achieved objective value of $f(\mathbf{x}) = 0.0019$

This procedure was done with target values from 0 to 1 in steps of 0.1. Figure 10 shows the resulting deformed meshes for the different target values (including the achieved score from the objective function) in superposition to the reference mesh.

Figure 10: Resulting meshes depending on the target value, with the achieved objective value $f(x)$ indicating the difference to the respective desired target value for the double sine reference mesh.

For all target values except $T_v = 1$, the optimization algorithm found a solution matching the specified target RMS value. For a uniform starting point $\mathbf{x}_0 = [0, 0, \dots, 0] \in \mathbb{R}^{16}$, the deformed meshes for $T_v = 0$ to $T_v = 0.5$ only show varying degrees of the same geometric shape. This indicates that the algorithm found the same local minimum for those target values, converging toward it to varying degrees. To mitigate this behavior, alternative starting points can be selected for those configurations to guide the algorithm toward a different local optimum. In case of $T_v = 1$, the RMS value only deviates by about 0.2 % from the target. Looking at the superposition of the reference and the deformed mesh in Figure 10, the meshes only deviate slightly. From a manufacturing perspective, these slight deviations from the desired tool shape will not affect the draping result drastically. The precision of the draping tool is therefore sufficient for the generation of tools with different degrees of similarity.

Usecase 2. Similar to *Usecase 1*, the surface modification was done using a parabolic geometry as reference mesh and a planar geometry as deformable mesh. Figure 11 shows an exemplary deformation result for $T_v = 1$ including the hull and the modified spline control points.

Figure 11: (a) Initial mesh and (b) deformed configuration for $T_v = 1$ with an achieved objective value of $f(x) = 0.0018$.

Again, for each target value from 0 to 1 (in steps of 0.1), a deformed configuration was calculated. As for *Usecase 1*, the algorithm found solutions matching the specified target value, except for $T_v = 1$. Since for this usecase, the solver also tends to converge to the same local minimum (but to different extents) for target values below $T_v = 0.5$, only selected results are shown in Figure 12:

Figure 12: Resulting meshes depending on the target value, with the achieved objective value $f(\mathbf{x})$ indicating the difference to the respective desired target value for the parabolic reference mesh.

To demonstrate the dependency of the solution on the chosen starting point \mathbf{x}_0 , Figure 13 shows different solutions calculated for $T_v = 0.5$ for different starting points \mathbf{x}_0 .

Figure 13: Resulting meshes for $T_v = 0.5$ depending on the starting point \mathbf{x}_0 (with the achieved objective value $f(\mathbf{x})$ for the parabolic reference mesh).

All resulting geometries match the desired T_v of 0.5. The starting point, however, influences the resulting shape. This emphasizes the need for further investigations concerning the selection of the starting point \mathbf{x}_0 . Beside that, the interaction between the three building blocks of the routine works quite well since linking the three components (FFD, similarity measure and optimization algorithm) provides a plausible set of configurations for the different target values and shapes can be controlled using different starting points.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The developed routine provides a robust, repeatable way to generate draping tools of different similarities for generic shapes such as a double sine and a parabolic geometry. There is still potential for improvement concerning the tendency of solutions within a certain target to converge to the same solution but with varying degrees. A detailed study on the starting point \mathbf{x}_0 selection as well as a more in-depth analysis on the penalty function are planned for future studies to guide the optimization algorithm toward different local optimum solutions from the outset. Additional next steps are to include real component tools in the representative tool set. If this step works out well, the U-Net surrogate model explained in [1] should be trained with the different tools and the prediction quality should be evaluated.

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